

Open Elites: Open Science Practices among Scientific Elites

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Background

Scientific elites are distinguished professionals and experts within their fields who possess extensive knowledge, expertise, and a demonstrated record of accomplishment of groundbreaking contributions to scientific research and discovery. Due to their esteemed status and impact in the scientific community, their significant efforts to the advancement of scientific knowledge, their role in networking and connecting people, and their power and position in the academic and non-academic settings, scientific elites frequently serve as leaders and trendsetters within their respective scientific domains. Consequently, their practices serve as exemplary models for scientific communities to emulate and follow, owing to their ability to forge connections, wield power and influence, and navigate both academic and non-academic landscapes. Therefore, analyzing the patterns that govern the trajectories of scientific elites is important in terms of the impact of these patterns on different communities. One of the important practices in the academia that needs attention is the extent to which scientists, in particular, scientific elites care about open science.

Objectives

This study aims to examine the extent to which scientific elites prioritize and engage in open science practices. By exploring the current patterns, this research seeks to shed light on the attitudes and behaviors of scientific elites towards open science. The objective is to provide insights into the adoption and promotion of open science practices among scientific elites, considering their significant influence, networking capabilities, and positions within academic and non-academic settings. By focusing on this

important aspect of academia, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of the role of scientific elites in shaping and advancing open science trends. To fulfill the primary goal, the specific objectives of this study are as follows:

1. Identify the extent to which scientific elites prioritize and engage in open access publishing, with a focus on their publication practices and preferences.
2. Examine the adoption and utilization of preprint servers by scientific elites, assessing the frequency and significance of preprint dissemination in their research.
3. Explore the level of participation of scientific elites in open review reports, evaluating their involvement in providing open feedback and open peer review reports.
4. Explore the extent to which scientific elites embrace open data practices, including data sharing, data management, and accessibility of research data.

Methodology

Scientific elites refer to highly accomplished and influential professionals within their respective scientific fields. However, there is no universally agreed-upon operational definition of scientific elites. The term "scientific elites" is subjective and can vary depending on context and perspective. In general, it refers to individuals who have reached the pinnacle of their scientific careers, often characterized by their exceptional achievements, extensive expertise, significant contributions to scientific knowledge, and widespread recognition within their fields.

In the current study, Highly Cited Researchers (HCRs), who are recognized for their significant influence and impact in the scientific community

based on their citation metrics, are considered as a subset of scientific elites. Their inclusion in the study allows for a focused analysis of a specific group of accomplished researchers who have consistently produced influential and highly cited research in their respective fields. This study will explore the 2022 list of HCRs¹, which is the most recent published edition and includes 6938 researchers, and draw 607 random samples (Confidence Level: 99% and Confidence Interval: 5)² for investigating their open science practices.

To gather the necessary data, a search will be conducted for the Highly Cited Researchers (HCRs) using their names or unique identifiers such as ResearcherID, ORCID, and Scopus Author ID. The search will be conducted on platforms including Web of Science and Scopus, which will provide information on preprints and open access publishing practices. Additionally, Publons will be utilized to gather data on open review reports. To collect information on open data practices, repositories such as Dryad Digital Repository, figshare, Harvard Dataverse Network, Kaggle, Network Data Exchange (NDEX), Open Science Framework, and Zenodo will be explored. These sources will serve as valuable resources for obtaining comprehensive data on the open science practices of the identified HCRs. The collected data will be analyzed through Microsoft Office Excel and SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) package.

Findings

The study anticipates uncovering the extent to which scientific elites prioritize and engage in open access publishing. The findings may reveal the proportion of HCRs who actively publish their research in open access journals or make their publications freely available through preprint servers. The findings might indicate the frequency and significance of preprint dissemination in the work of HCRs, shedding light on their preferences and practices related to sharing preliminary research findings. In addition, the findings may provide insights into the extent to which HCRs actively engage in providing open feedback and peer review reports, indicating their willingness to contribute to transparent and collaborative evaluation processes. Moreover, the findings may reveal the

level of involvement of HCRs in data sharing, data management, and the accessibility of research data, providing insights into their contributions to open and reproducible science.

Conclusion

The scientific elites are important individuals to shape the landscape of academia. By exploring open science practices among scientific elites, the research seeks to illuminate their level of commitment to open science principles, their advocacy for open research, and their dedication to fostering transparency and accountability in scientific endeavors.

Comments

This initial study marks the beginning of a series aiming to illuminate the adoption of open science practices (open access, open review reports, open education, open data, etc.) within the scientific elite community (such as HCRs, Nobel laureates, Top 2% Scientist, etc.